

GALLSTONE ILEUS DUE TO CHOLECYSTODUODENAL FISTULA: TWO CASE REPORTS

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Keywords

Cholecysto-duodenal fistula,

Gallstone,

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ABSTRACT

Gallstone ileus, a rare and unique cause of intestinal obstruction, is the focus of our discussion. We present a case of a patient who arrived at our emergency department with complaints of abdominal pain, nausea, and vomiting. To manage this rare condition, the patient underwent enterotomy, cholecystectomy, and primary duodenal repair. This case is discussed in the context of current literature, highlighting our medical case's unique and specialized nature.

INTRODUCTION

Gallstone ileus, a rare complication of cholelithiasis, was first described by Bartholin in 1654^{1,2}. It accounts for 1-4% of all cases of intestinal obstruction and 25% of non-strangulated intestinal obstructions in patients over 65^{3,4}. Cholecystoduodenal fistula, the most common type of bilioenteric fistula, is responsible for 76% of gallstone ileus cases. Other types of fistulas include cholecystocholic (11%), cholecystogastric (6%), choledochoduodenal (4%), and cholecystocholedochal (3%)^{4,5}. Gallstone ileus is observed in 0.3-0.5% of all cases of cholelithiasis^{4,5}. While 80% of gallstones passing into the intestinal tract through a bilioenteric fistula are excreted without causing significant issues, an obstruction occurs when the stone exceeds 2.5 cm in diameter. Typically, the obstruction occurs in the terminal ileum (70%), followed by less frequent occurrences in the proximal ileum, jejunum, colon, and duodenum⁷. Gallstone ileus often presents with a fatal course, with a mortality rate of approximately 15%, mainly due to advanced age, comorbidities, and delayed diagnosis⁸. This case report examines a patient with a gallstone ileus presentation and discusses the diagnosis and management approach in light of current literature.

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CASE 1

A 52-year-old female patient was admitted to the emergency department of our hospital with a 3-day history of abdominal pain, nausea, and vomiting. Physical examination revealed abdominal distension and diffuse tenderness. Fecaloid content was observed through nasogastric drainage. Laboratory tests showed a white blood cell count of 12,700. Liver function tests and bilirubin levels were regular. Imaging revealed multiple millimetric calculi in the gallbladder, air densities in the intrahepatic bile ducts, and a 3.5 × 3 cm calcified calculus with proximal jejunal dilatation. The patient was diagnosed with gallstone ileus, and an emergency surgery was performed. During the surgery, we found chronic cholecystitis and a cholecysto-duodenal fistula between the gallbladder fundus and the first part of the duodenum. The gallbladder fundus was separated from the duodenal wall, and a fistula-related perforation was noted in the duodenum. We removed the gallbladder and repaired the duodenal perforation.

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We also removed the large gallstone that was causing the obstruction. The patient recovered well and was discharged without complications.

Oral intake was started, drains were removed, and the patient was discharged on the seventh day without complications, reinforcing the effectiveness of our management strategies.

The successful management of the case was evident as the patient passed gas and stool on the third postoperative day.

Figure I. CT scan of gallstone ileus (Case 1)

Figure II. CT scan of gallstone ileus (Case 1)

Figure III. During operation: cholecystoduodenal fistula (Case 1)

Figure IV. Gallstone (Case 1)

CASE 2

A 52-year-old male patient presented to the emergency department with a 2-day history of abdominal pain, nausea, vomiting, and inability to pass urine. Physical examination revealed diffuse abdominal tenderness and a distended abdomen. Rectal examination was unremarkable. Laboratory tests showed a white blood cell count of 12,200, and liver function tests were routine. Computed tomography revealed air-fluid levels in the small intestines and a calcified gallstone located in the jejunum, approximately 4 × 5 cm. The MRCP report suggested increased gallbladder wall thickness, irregularity, and possible perforation. The patient underwent a laparotomy. On exploration, severe jejunal dilatation was noted. A 4 × 6 cm gallstone was found in the proximal jejunum, causing obstruction. Enterectomy was performed to remove the stone. Further exploration revealed a fistula between the gallbladder and duodenum. Retrograde cholecystectomy was performed, and the duodenal fistula was repaired with a double-layer closure. The surgery was completed with the placement of an abdominal drain. On the fourth postoperative day, the patient passed gas and stool, and oral liquid food was started. The abdominal drain was removed on the sixth postoperative day. The patient was discharged on the seventh postoperative day without complications.

DISCUSSION

Gallstone ileus occurs when gallstones pass into the intestinal tract and cause obstruction due to a fistula between the gallbladder or biliary tract and the duodenum, stomach, choledochus, or colon⁹. Preoperative diagnosis is challenging because other obstruction causes must be considered first, and there are no specific clinical or laboratory findings. As more than half of the patients have comorbidities, such as cardiac disease, diabetes, or obesity, mortality and morbidity rates are high^{5, 10}. Radiologically, air-fluid levels compatible with obstruction in the small intestine are observed, but etiological findings such as pneumobilia and ectopically located gallstones are often absent¹¹. Pneumobilia is present in 30-40% of radiologic findings. Findings of a cholecystoduodenal fistula are usually not identified by conventional radiological methods. In our case, pneumobilia was detected on tomography and MRCP, which served as a warning sign in the differential diagnosis of ileus due to gallstone obstruction. A review of 67 articles published between 1950 and 1985, which included a total of 1,061 cases, revealed that the

gallstone was located in the terminal ileum in 64% of cases, the proximal ileum and jejunum in 23%, the colon in 4%, and the stomach in 1%¹⁴. The most common location of the fistula is the cholecystoduodenal fistula (68%), followed by cholecystocolonic (5%) and cholecystoduodenocolic fistulas (5%)¹⁴. Consistent with these findings in the literature.

A cholecystoduodenal fistula was identified during exploration in our case. Both surgical exploration and imaging showed that the gallstone was lodged in the jejunum in our patient.

The primary goal in treating gallstone ileus is to relieve the obstruction. Studies comparing single and two-stage surgical strategies for emergency treatment indicate that both approaches can be performed safely with zero mortality¹². However, in general, mortality in single-stage treatment can be as high as 19%, while no mortality has been observed in two-stage operations^{13, 14}. Case reports in the literature suggest that stones lodged in the intestinal system can be manually directed toward the colon and removed via the anal canal⁶.

Given the young age of our patient, the absence of comorbidities, and the suitability of surgical exploration, we performed cholecystectomy, primary duodenal repair, and stone extraction via enterotomy in the same surgical session. Our patient was discharged on the seventh postoperative day without complications.

CONCLUSION

Gallstone ileus should be considered in the differential diagnosis of patients presenting with signs of intestinal obstruction. Depending on the patient's general condition, comorbidities, and age, various surgical procedures can be performed. Enterolithotomy, cholecystectomy, and fistula tract repair can be carried out as a single- or two-stage surgical approach.

REFERENCES

1. Doko M, Zovak M, Kopljar M, et al. Comparison of surgical treatments of gallstone ileus: preliminary report. *World J Surg* 2003; 27(4): 400-404
2. Way LW. Surgical diagnosis and treatment. Biliary tract. Current. 10th edition. Appleton and Lange 1994: 553-554
3. Bourke MJ, Scheider DM, Haber GB. Electrohydraulic lithotripsy of gallstone causing gallstone ileus. *Gastrointest Endosc* 1997; 45: 521-523
4. Cooper SG, Sherman SB, Steinhardt JE, Wilson JM, Richman AH. Bouveret's syndrome: Diagnostic considerations. *JAMA* 1987; 286: 226

5. Reisner RM, Cohen JR. Gallstone ileus: A review of 1001 reported cases. *Am Surg* 1994; 60(6): 441-446
6. Agresta F, Bedin N. Gallstone ileus as a complication of acute cholecystitis. Laparoscopic diagnosis and treatment. *Surg Endosc* 2002; 16(11): 1637-1641
7. Khaira HS, Thomas DR. Gallstone emesis and ileus caused by common hepatic ductoduodenal fistula. *Br J Surg* 1994; 81: 723
8. Clavien PA, Richon J, Burgan S, Rohner A. Gallstone ileus. *Br J Surg* 1990; 77: 737
9. Yamada T, Alpers DH, Owyang C. Textbook of Gastroenterology. Diseases of the biliary tree—Biliary fistula. 2013
10. Rodriguez-Sanjuán JC, Casado F, Fernandez MJ, Morales DJ, Naranjo A. Cholecystectomy and fistula closure versus enterolithotomy alone in gallstone ileus. *Br J Surg* 1997; 84(5): 634-637
11. Nakamoto Y, Saga T, Fjishiro S, et al. Gallstone ileus with impaction at the neck of a Meckel's diverticulum. *Br J Radiol* 1998; 71: 1320-1322
12. Schwartz SI, Shires GT, Spencer FC, et al. Principles of surgery. Gallbladder and extrahepatic system. McGraw Hill; 1999: 1450-1452
13. Tan YM, Wong WK, Ooi LL. A comparison of two surgical strategies for the emergency treatment of gallstone ileus. *Singapore Med J* 2004; 45 (2): 69-72
14. Kasahara Y, Umemura H, Shiraha S, et al. Gallstone ileus. Review of 112 patients in the Japanese literature. *Am J Surg* 1980; 140(3): 437-440
15. Clavien PA, Richon J, Burgan S, Rohner A. Gallstone ileus. *Br J Surg* 1990; 77(7): 737-742